

Rearrangement of N-Chlorobenzanilide

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Rates for rearrangement of N-chlorobenzanilide increase with increase in acid concentration in the range 0.5 to 3.0M hydrochloric and sulphuric acids. The reaction is first order with respect to substrate concentration, H⁺ ion concentration and is photochemically sensitive. Overall reaction is governed by acid catalysed rates except at ionic strength 1.5μ. Bunnett and Bunnett-Olsen plot data show dependence of rates on water activity. Formation of benzoic acid from hydrolysis of N-chlorobenzanilide shows that chlorine does not migrate to this part of the molecule.

THE conversion of N-chloroacetanilide and its derivatives into a mixture of nuclear substituted derivatives in presence of hydrochloric and sulphuric acid in hydroxylic solvents has been studied¹⁻⁶. Bell and his coworkers studied rearrangements of N-bromobenzanilide in aprotic solvents using a variety of phenols and carboxylic acids as catalyst⁷⁻¹⁰.

A survey of literature revealed that no work has been done on rearrangement of N-halobenzanilide and its derivatives. The present paper describes the kinetic study of rearrangement of N-chlorobenzanilide. The nature of acid catalysis and migration of chlorine have been discussed. A probable mechanism has been formulated on the basis of available kinetic data.

Experimental

N-Chlorobenzanilide (m.p. 166°) was prepared by usual methods¹¹ and characterized as usual by estimation of active chlorine (% active chlorine: Calcd. 15.33; Found, 15.24). Rates of disappearance of N-chlorobenzanilide (0.001M) in 40% acetic acid-water mixtures were followed by withdrawing aliquots at suitable intervals and titrating active chlorine (on addition of KI) iodometrically. Deuterium oxide of isotopic purity >99.5% was obtained from B.A.R.C., Trombay. All reagents were of A.R. grade.

Results and Discussion

The rates for the rearrangement of N-chlorobenzanilide into nuclear substituted derivative increase with increase in concentration of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids (Table 1). Rates are proportional to H⁺ ion concentration rather than H₀. This indicates bimolecular nature of the reaction, with nucleophilic attack of water molecule¹². Bunnett (log K + H₀ or log K - log CH⁺ against log aH₂O) and Bunnett Olsen (log K + H₀ against log CH⁺H₀)

TABLE 1—REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROBENZANILIDE IN ACIDS

(M) acid	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
	1 : 6.75					
HCl	4.38	8.96	10.09	12.98	—	18.95
	2 : 10.58					
H ₂ SO ₄	—	1.86	2.58	3.21	3.76	4.31

k = 10⁴ sec⁻¹, (1, dark., 2, U.V. light)

plot data give slopes which indicate the dependence of rates on water activity^{13,14}.

Increase in rates with increase in acid concentration indicates acid catalysis. However the increase of rates may also be due to ionic acceleration.

In order to investigate the cause of increase of rates, kinetic runs were performed at different constant ionic strengths using mixtures of hydrochloric acid-sodium chloride (Table 2).

TABLE 2—RATES FOR THE REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROBENZANILIDE AT CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH IN HCl-NaCl AT 35°

HCl	NaCl	μ	10 ⁴ × k(sec ⁻¹)
0.2	0.8	0.5	3.7
0.3	0.2	0.5	4.9
0.4	0.1	0.5	7.2
0.5	0.5	1.0	7.7
0.6	0.4	1.0	9.2
0.7	0.3	1.0	10.7
0.8	1.0	1.5	7.9
1.0	0.5	1.5	10.9
1.3	0.2	1.5	12.5

Following conclusions have been derived from ionic strength effect data : (i) increase in rates with increase in acid concentration indicates acid catalysis and susceptibility of these rates to ionic strength effect ; (ii) neutral rates do not contribute except at ionic strength 1.5μ and (iii) reaction is

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subject to negative ionic strength effect since decrease in slopes with increase in ionic strength has been observed.

The total rate for the rearrangement can be represented (neglecting the contribution from neutral rates), by the equation¹⁵ :

$$K_e = kH_0 \cdot \exp.(bH^+/\mu) \cdot CH^+$$

The values for kH_0 (specific acid catalysed rates constant at zero ionic strength) and bH^+ have been evaluated as 3.51 and -0.50 respectively. Acid catalysed rates were then calculated, using above equation but did not agree well with the experimental rates.

An increase in rates with increase in ionic radii of cation (Table 3) has been attributed to specific salt effect¹⁶. A probable explanation may be the electrostatic attraction of cation by the negative nitrogen of N-chlorobenzanilide which reduces the charge density on nitrogen. This effect increases with decrease of charge density i.e., with increase of ionic radii. Similar results were observed in the hydrolysis of mono 2 : 4 dichlorophenyl phosphate.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CATIONS ON REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROBENZANILIDE

Cations	Ionic radii	$10^4 k \text{ sec}^{-1}$
Li ⁺	0.60	5.85
Na ⁺	0.95	7.64
K ⁺	1.33	12.64

Rates for rearrangement in solvent deuterium oxide gave $^kD_2O/^kH_2O > 1$. This shows a pre-equilibrium fast proton transfer generally observed for acid catalysed reactions¹⁷. Rates of rearrangement of N-chlorobenzanilide increase with increase in substrate concentration (Table 4). Values for k ,

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTRATE ON THE REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROBENZANILIDE

Substrate (M)	$10^4 k \text{ sec}^{-1}$	k_2
0.001	8.96	0.89
0.002	13.45	0.67
0.003	18.22	0.60

when plotted against substrate concentration, gave a straight line. The values of k_2 have been found to be nearly the same. For obtaining dependence of rates on H^+ concentration, k'_2 and k_2 values have been calculated (Table 5). Plots of k_2 against H^+ ion concentration give straight line with zero origin. k'_2 values have been found to be nearly constant. Thus it can be concluded that rates for rearrangement are dependent on H^+ ion concentration.

TABLE 5—VARIATION OF RATES WITH H^+ ION CONCENTRATION

	(M)	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
HCl	k_2	0.43	0.89	1.00	1.23	—	0.99
	k'_2	0.87	0.89	0.67	0.61	—	0.46
H_2SO_4	k_2	—	0.18	0.25	0.32	0.37	0.43
	k'_2	—	0.18	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.14

($k_2 = \text{L.M.}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$; $k'_2 = \text{L.M.}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$)

The rates for rearrangement of N-chlorobenzanilide were studied in dark, day light and uv light. An increase in rates has been observed by the effect of light. This shows that the compound is photochemically sensitive. This is probable since it has been stated that the rearrangement of N-chloroacetanilide is accelerated by light and radicals such as Br, Cl, NO_2 attached to nitrogen change places under the influence of sunlight with a hydrogen atom in nucleus¹⁸.

Hydrolysis of N-chlorobenzanilide gave *p*-chloro aniline and benzoic acid without chlorine. This shows that chlorine of N-Cl does not migrate in this part of the molecule.

Rearrangement of N-chlorobenzanilide is thus a bimolecular acid catalysed reaction and involves participation of water molecule. Bimolecular nature of reaction is also supported by the magnitudes of Arrhenius parameters. A decrease in rates of rearrangement with varying concentration of phenol (Table 6) shows the formation of hypochlorous acid and thus the role of water molecule in rearrangement is justified.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATION OF PHENOL ON THE REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROBENZANILIDE

Phenol (M)	HCl (M)	$10^4 k \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.005	1.0	27.99
0.01	"	25.79
0.02	"	23.60

Since phenols do not react with hydrochloric acid the decrease of rates with increase in concentration of phenol shows that hypochlorous acid formed by the action of water molecule on chlorine of N-Cl bond reacts with increasing concentration of phenol and causes a decrease of rates.

On the basis of results discussed above, following mechanism can be formulated for the acid catalysed rearrangement of N-chlorobenzanilide in hydrochloric and sulphuric acids (Scheme Z)

SCHEME—Z

(i) ACID CATALYSED REARRANGEMENT IN HYDROCHLORIC ACID

(ii) ACID CATALYSED REARRANGEMENT IN SULPHURIC ACID

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References

1. K. J. P. ORTON and M. J. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 25.
2. K. J. P. ORTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 1456, 1911, 1185.
3. M. D. PATWARDHAN, S. D. SHARMA, B. K. GUPTA and M. M. MHALA, *Jwaji University*, 1976, 4, 21.
4. M. D. PATWARDHAN, S. D. SHARMA, B. K. GUPTA and M. M. MHALA, *Vijnana Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1975, 18, 289.
5. M. D. PATWARDHAN, S. D. SHARMA, B. K. GUPTA and M. M. MHALA, *Vijnana Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1976, 19, 25.
6. M. D. PATWARDHAN, M. M. MHALA, B. K. GUPTA and S. D. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 284.
7. R. P. BELL, *Proc. Royal Soc.*, 1934, 143, 377.
8. R. P. BELL and P. LEVINGE, *Proc. Royal Soc.*, 1935.
9. R. P. BELL and P. V. DANCKWERTS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1774.
10. R. P. BELL and P. LIDWELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1096.
11. R. A. BARNES and O. W. PORTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1731.
12. C. P. HAMMETT, "Physical Organic Chemistry", Mc. Graw Hill Co., 1940.
13. J. F. BUNNETT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4956.
14. J. F. BUNNETT and F. P. OLSEN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1966, 44, 1917.
15. M. M. MHALA and M. D. PATWARDHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 360.
16. M. M. MHALA, S. S. BHATWEDKAR and R. N. SHARMA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, 44, 668.
17. R. P. BELL, "Acid Base Catalysis", Oxford University Press, London, 1941.
18. J. H. MATHEWS and R. V. WILLIAMSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 2574.